

Special Health Smart Cards Scheme Government Benefit to Korga's Primitive Tribal Group Mangalore District in Karnataka

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Abstract-

Health is one of the fundamental basic needs of all human beings. It is a positive state of wellbeing rather than a negative state of mere absence of disease. The concern for better health care is universal. Health is primary requisite of a person. Health is a function of not only medical care, but also of a person, overall integrated development of society. Health is another important ingredient of human development. It determines both the longevity and the quality of life. Health also impacts learning outcomes, functioning capability and earning capacity of the people. Ill-health can lead to deprivation in capability which results in low work efficiency and hence poverty. Poverty, caused by poor health, can further adds fuel to ill health through low food intake, nutritional deficiency, deprivation of basic amenities (safe drinking water, sanitation, drainage, etc.,) causing a colossal loss of financial as well as human resources (GoI, 2011). The United Nations, people oriented 'Millennium Development Goals' concluded in the year 2015, which triggered new initiatives in the form of 'Sustainable Development Goals (SDG)' with a continuing mandate to "Ensure healthy lives and promoting well-being for all, at all ages". The focus towards achieving Universal Health Coverage for ensuring the wellbeing of all was expressly underpinned in this goal

Introduction

Good health not only promotes human development but it also allows people to attend work regularly and to be productive at work and thereby less vulnerable to poverty. Poor countries tend to be unhealthy, and unhealthy countries tend to be poor. Ensuring equitable and quality health and medical care services will go a long way in human development and quality of life.(GOK2015)A small initiative by the State Government of Karnataka. After all, for an individual who believes in the maxim "Health is Wealth", and has to live by it, there could be greater gift. Health is a state of complete physical mental and social wellbeing and is not merely absence of disease or infirmity". There are four major determinants of health, namely, heredity, nutrition, environmental and lifestyles. Except heredity, all other factors are within the control of the individual and the community. Health is an important component of economic development of a nation. Health is the most essential component of human life. Better health status leads to better productivity. The development of health is holistic process related to the overall growth and development of social, cultural, economic, educational and environmental factors. Healthy citizens are economically useful, progressive, and productive and thus, are an asset to the nation. Better the

quality of citizens, better the quality of life. One of the major concerns of health organizations world over in general and India in particular is to provide sound health to every individual. In India the state government primarily provides health services. However, the Union Government contributes substantially through grants and centrally sponsored health programmes.

The main objectives of the study

1. To examine Primitive Tribal Groups to avail health benefits in assorted hospitals in Mangalore in Karnataka
2. To recognition of Health Smart Cards the prevalent Korga's families Healthcare.ITDP district of D.K in Karnataka

The area of the Study and maps

The Dakshina Kannada (erstwhile South Kanara) is one of the three coastal districts of Karnataka State with a geographical area of 4859 sq. Km. Located between the foothills of Western Ghats in the east and Arabian sea in the west, it is bordered by Udupi District to the north, Chikkamagaluru district to the northeast, Hassan District to the east, Kodagu to the southeast, and Kasaragod District in Kerala state to the south. The district has five taluks namely, Bantwal, Belthangady, Mangaluru, Puttur and Sullia. Mangaluru city is the district headquarters and the main city of the district.

historically, socially and economically deprived communities. The Central and the State Governments have implemented several multifaceted and multi-pronged programmes for social and economic welfare of the STs to bring them into the mainstream development. Most of the government social programmes implemented have been found successful in provision of the basic livelihood amenities to the STs in the district. They are, at present not lagging very much behind other communities as regards primary and secondary education, housing, safe drinking water supply, electricity and sanitation. They, however, still lag behind the rest of the population in higher and professional education, access to healthcare facilities, high-end job market, access to productive assets and credit, business enterprises and standard of living. Most of them remained resource poor and in low-end labour jobs. The setting up separate colonies for STs with all infrastructures, though good, has adverse effect on their integration into mainstream society. Another important emerging issue is the existence of wide gaps among the sub-castes of the STs. All sub-casts among STs have not benefitted from government programmes equally. Among the STs, Koragas are still far behind economically and socially compared to other ST groups. The Tribal Sub-Plan was first introduced in 1976-77 when it

was implemented in five Integrated Tribal Development Projects (ITDP) in the districts of Mysore, Chikmagalur, Kodagu and Dakshina Kannada (including Udupi). The second largest tribal groups are found in the state of Karnataka. The Koragas of Dakshina Kannada district classified as “primitive tribes”. The Koraga community is considered as 'Adivasis' (aboriginal natives) of erstwhile undivided Dakshina Kannada district. In 1956, the community was declared as STs and in 1986; they were treated as Primitive Tribal Group (PTG). The majority of the Koraga Community is residing in Udupi, DK and Kasargod districts.

Scheduled Tribes Groups in Mangalore District, Karnataka

The STs in the district include mainly Koragas, Malekudiyas and Marathi Naikas. Koragas are known as the original natives of erstwhile Dakshina Kannada district. They are distinctly different from others in the district in life style, cultural habits and traditional practices. In towns, they work as scavengers in the sanitary departments (DKDHR 2014) In recent years, they are employed by the sanitary department as scavengers in urban areas. The ITDP, Zilla Panchayat carried out a survey of Koraga community in the district and as per their study the taluk-wise distribution of the Koraga community is as given in Table No :1

Table No:1 Taluk-wise Population of Koraga Community in Mangalore district 2011

S.No	Taluks	Families (number)	Population			
			Male	Female	Total	Families rank in district
1	Mangaluru city	271	621	583	1204	2
2	Mangaluru (Rural)	503	1088	1114	2202	1
3	Bantwal	187	294	278	572	3
4	Belthangady	100	206	190	396	4
5	Puttur	113	195	188	383	5
6	Sullia	32	61	40	101	6
	District	1206	2465	2393	4858	-

Source: I.T.D.P. Zilla Panchayat, Dakshina Kannada District.

In the district, there are around 1,206 Koraga families including 774 families in Mangalore (urban-271, rural-503)The Nearly 70 percent (3406) of the community live in Mangaluru taluk. Sullia has the lowest number of Koraga families (32). Bantwal has 187 Koraga families, followed by Puttur (113). Sullia has the lowest number of Koraga families (32) Bantwal has 187, followed by Puttur, 113 families and Belthangady, 100 families.

Health smart cards is one of the prevalent korgas person Healthcare Scheme in the district. Offering a low priced product for a wide range of surgical cover, nearly 823 defined surgical procedures to the Korgas family members. It is a contributory scheme wherein the beneficiaries contribute a ITDP programmes every year to avail any possible surgery during the period. The beneficiaries are offered cashless treatment subject to conditions of the scheme at the

important Network Hospitals reach from corner to corner the Mangalore district.

Health Smart Cards Interest Group Benefit Scheme Mangalore District in Karnataka

The distribution of smart cards to all Koraga families, the dream project of ITDP. The card will be of immense help to the Koraga tribals members, as it contains information of the patient's last 50 treatments. The card operates on biometric identification system. The cardholder can use it in some of the hospitals in the district. The Cards also help to avail any other facilities which are being offered by ITDP for Koragas. Those who have not got smart cards can claim health benefits at recognised hospitals using a letter from the department. Though government releases cost of treatment directly to hospitals under an arrangement now, the institutions provide treatment only after obtaining approval from the government case by case. Approvals take time as District Health Officer (DHO) will have to approve them after receiving the documents such as scans. Under the proposed scheme, this can be done online. This will become possible when authorities digitise data about them and issue smart cards under the Vinutana (New) scheme. At present, smart card registrations, information verification and data compilations are on in full-swing as the Integrated Tribal Development Project (ITDP). It will benefit nearly 1,206 families or 4,858 persons — who come under the community recognised as a Primitive Tribal Group in the district. They can avail treatment at select private hospitals, the cost of which the department reimburses.

This (the new system) allows the process of approval to be much faster. The physician understood around 70 per cent of the information collected from the Koragas has been digitised so far; while smart cards have been distributed to 30 per cent of the Koraga population. Smart card would help Koragas to avail health benefits in various hospitals in Mangalore district in Karnataka. The distribution of smart cards to all Koraga families, the dream project of ITDP. The card will be of immense help to the Koraga tribals members, as it contains information of the patient's last 50 treatments. The Physician also said that a maternal death rate in this community is higher than other communities. The surgery persons find out that smart cards have been distributed to all the members of the community and the details of the individuals will be available online within two months. Since the past one and half years Rs 45 lacs have been

spent for the treatment of 89 families of this Koraga community.

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- Offering a low priced product for a wide range of surgical cover, nearly 823 clear surgical procedures to the Korgas family members.
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Distribution Smart Cards to PTGs Mangalore District in Karnataka

The Healthcare in India has undergone a sea-change in the last decade and today with the launch of Health smart cards scheme, it has touched the heart of Karnataka, the PTGs Mangalore. A small initiative by the State Government of Karnataka. After all, for an individual who believes in the maxim "Health is Wealth", and has to live by it, there could be greater gift. Since the launch in April, 2012, a total of 53 persons from the Koraga community have availed this facility, with a total disbursement of Rs. 25.68 lakh having been approved so far. The ITDP decided to extend Universal Health Care in all the three sectors of primary, secondary and tertiary care to all Koraga Primitive Tribal Group t community residents of Mangalore district Karnataka by pooling resources from various on-going schemes. The public Distribution System (PDS) card Number with a separator (-) and a sequential number for each member of the family that approaches a PHI for service and seeks to get enrolled. The Primitive Tribal Health Card provided will contain Photo, Name, Unique Scheme ID and Basic Details of the Beneficiary. An SMS alert will also be sent to the Enrolled Patient to his mobile number wherever the mobile number has been shared with the registration personnel. Once the Scheme card is generated the patient can access the treatment under the "smart cards" scheme. The beneficiary will not be required to carry his Adhaar card or Food card the next time he visits the hospital for treatment. They are will be serviced based on the smart cards.

The smart cards have already been distributed to more than 3,862 Koraga community individuals.

The distribution of smart cards to all Koraga families, the dream project of ITDP is in final stage and the officials have directed the taluk-level wardens to collect the data of remaining 149 Koraga families of Dakshina Kannada

district within October (Deccan Herald, 2014) The Dakshina Kannada district is blessed with good health infrastructure and enviable public-private initiatives in provision of healthcare service.

Table No: 2 Koraga Primitive Tribal Group to Health Benefits Hospitals Mangalore District in Karnataka

S.No	Name of the Hospitals	Taluk
1	Kasthribha Medical Collage	Mangalore
2	Father Muller's Hospital	
3	AJ Hospital	
4	Yenepoya Hospital	
5	Srinivas Hospital	
6	Global Hospital	
7	City Hospital	Puttur,
8	Benaka Hospital , Ujire,	Beltangady
9	Abhaya Hospital	Beltangady
10	KVG Hospital	Sullia.

Source: I.T.D.P. Dakshina Kannada District

The above table shows that Mangalore taluk in six reputed hospitals and Belatangadi taluk two Puttur and Sullia each one hospital avail health care in private hospitals without a long wait for approvals from health officials. After the launch last year, KVG Hospital in Sullia joined the list of private hospitals to offer the scheme in September. This is in addition to the tie-ups with A.J. Hospital and Research Centre, Father Muller Hospital and College, Kasturba Medical College, Yenepoya Hospital (all in Mangalore); Abhaya Hospital in Belthangady; and City Hospital in Puttur. A landmark initiative has come as a great boon to the Korgas in the district ,The Scheme is implemented for the PTGs their families. The Health Cards also help to avail any other facilities which are being offered by ITDP for Koragas. They can avail treatment at choose private hospitals, the cost of which the department reimburses

Problems the Health Cards to Korgas Primitive Tribal Group

The problem in collecting details of around 149 Koraga's families. Many families at Kerala border live a life of nomads. Whenever officials go to collect information.

Conclusion

The Health Security Card, a smart card, contains essential information for health care providers, and local, tribal, and state health departments to identify individuals, meet their immediate health needs, improve access critical data, and better obtain surveillance and situational awareness, thereby minimizing morbidity and mortality. Healthcare in India has undergone a sea-change in the last decade and today with the launch of Health smart cards

scheme, it has touched the heart of Karnataka. The landmark initiative has come as a great boon to the Korgas in the district .The Scheme is implemented for the PTGs their families. The Cards also help to avail any other facilities which are being offered by ITDP for Koragas. They can avail treatment at choose private hospitals, the cost of which the department reimburses.The Name of the PTGs korags through Integrated Tribal Development Programme district of Mangalore in Karnataka. The Smart card would help Koragas to avail health benefits in various hospitals in Mangalore distinct in Karnataka

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